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Corrigendum: Potentiation of brain-derived neurotrophic factor-induced protection of spiral ganglion neurons by C3 exoenzyme/Rho inhibitor

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In the published article, there was an error in the author list, and authors "Jennifer Harre and Laura Heinkele" were erroneously not marked as equally contributing and sharing first authorship. The corrected author list appears below.

"Jennifer Harre^{1,2*†}, Laura Heinkele^{1†}, Melanie Steffens¹, Athanasia Warnecke^{1,2}, Thomas Lenarz^{1,2}, Ingo Just³ and Astrid Rohrbeck³"

This also affects the **Author contributions** section within the published article. The corrected **Author contributions** section is below.

Author contributions

JH, AR, and AW designed the research. MS contributed to the initial experiments. LH performed the experiments and analyzed the data. JH, LH, and AW wrote the manuscript. JH and LH contributed equally. IJ and TL provided administrative support. All authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.

The authors apologize for this error and state that this does not change the scientific conclusions of the article in any way. The original article has been updated.

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